

Unlocking the Power of Attitude, Motivation, and EFL Speaking Performance among Grade 11 Students in Addis Ababa City, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

This study used the Pearson-product moment to examine the relationship between motivation, attitude, and speaking performance of EFL students of Addis Ababa City. In this regard, 87 Ethiopian grade 11 students were the sample of the population. Gardner's (1985) adaptation of the Attitude Motivation Test Battery served for the development of motivation and attitude surveys. Quantitative data were gathered via close-ended questionnaires of students' attitude and motivation. Data were also acquired utilizing speaking tests. These data were analyzed using SPSS version 24. The finding of this study showed that motivation, attitude and speaking performance have a significant relationship. Moreover, the ANOVA analysis revealed that there were statistically significant relationship among students' attitude, motivation and speaking performance. The correlation coefficient between speaking performance and attitude was found to be 0.828, with a P-value was less than 0.05. The outcome also showed that speaking performance and motivations had a relationship, with a correlation coefficient of 0.449 and a P-value was also less than 0.05. The results of multiple regression analysis revealed that from these variables of the study attitude was the stronger predictor of the speaking performance. Therefore, the results indicated that the null hypotheses (H₀) were rejected and alternative hypotheses (H₁) were accepted.

Keywords: Attitude, EFL, Motivation, Relationship, Speaking Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning involves a complex relationship of various psychological factors that influence students' language acquisition and performance. Attitude, motivation and speaking ability are among these variables that are particularly important because of their profound effects on learning. To create effective language acquisition interventions and support mechanisms, educators and policymakers must have a

thorough understanding of the links between these variables. Brown (1994) states that both internal and external emotional factors contribute to language learning success and the development of pedagogy. Additionally, Harmer (2007) clarified that a common explanation for students' reluctance to speak up is that they feel uncomfortable expressing themselves in public, particularly when asked for personal information or their thoughts.

The first variable that contributes to speaking performance is attitude; it is related to speaking performance. According to Gardner, Lanlonde, and Moorcroft (1985), one of the factors influencing learning a foreign language is attitude because it has an impact on the amount of effort pupils put into acquiring the language. As a result, students who view speaking English positively will engage in speaking activities more and may try to use more coping strategies to get through challenging conversations; students who view speaking English negatively will be less likely to engage in speaking activities. Scholars from a wide range of disciplines, including psychology, communication studies, linguistics, and education, have researched attitudes and speaking performance in great detail. Additionally, Oller (1979) states that attitude is one of the factors that lead to motivation to learn a foreign language and helps in obtaining proficiency in the language. Furthermore, attitude is defined by Dorney and Ushioda (2011) as learners' general assessment or sentiment on language acquisition, taking into account factors like motivation, curiosity, confidence, and perceived utility of the language.

In this study motivation is considered as one of the significant features of second language acquisition which is considered as it has relationship with speaking performance of the students. If the learner does not have a desire to learn a language, it is very problematic to teach a second language. This concept indicates that motivation plays a pivotal role in learning any language skill. In this regard, some of the scholars' views concerning motivation are articulated in the following section.

In light of this, Nunan (1999) claims that motivation is a psychological desire that propels people to action. Motivation is a crucial component that affects students' learning outcomes, processes, and willingness when learning a language. It is also closely linked to learning success or failure (Dörnyei, 2014). According to Gardner (1985), a crucial factor in assessing a student's readiness for communication is motivation. Sidik (2013) claims that speaking has a connection to motivation, and self-confidence in communication. Motivation is defined by Babby (2015) as the level of effort and intensity put forth to achieve a goal. "A process which cannot be observed directly, but can be inferred by behaviors as a choice of tasks, effort, persistence, and verbalization," is how Pintrich & Schunk (1996:4) define motivation.

The second variable that contributes to speaking performance is attitude; it is also related to speaking performance. According to Gardner, Lanlonde, and Moorcroft (1985), one of the factors influencing learning a foreign language is attitude because it has an impact on the amount of effort pupils put into acquiring the language. As a result, students who view speaking English positively will engage in speaking activities more and may try to use more coping strategies to get through challenging conversations; students who view speaking English negatively will be less likely to engage in speaking activities.

Academics from a wide range of disciplines, including psychology, communication studies, linguistics, and education, have researched attitudes and speaking performance in great detail. Additionally, Oller (1979) states that attitude is one of the factors that lead to motivation to learn a foreign language and helps in obtaining proficiency in the language. Furthermore, attitude is defined by Dorney and Ushioda (2011) as learners' general assessment or sentiment on language acquisition, taking into account factors like motivation, curiosity, confidence, and perceived utility of the language.

Another point that is to be included in this paper is speaking performance which is relevant in this study. The performance is diverse and exhibits the capacity to switch between several semantic registers. According to Carlson (1996), achieving success and excellence in anything one does requires performing to a high standard.

Brown (2000) asserts that speaking performance, motivation and attitude are significantly correlated, especially while learning a second language. This notion reveals that speaking performance of students, attitude and motivation have potential relationship.

By the same token, although orientations, attitudes, and L2 proficiency were planned to be directly causally correlated in Gardner and Lambert's (1972) initial model, Gardner's subsequent conceptualization postulated that motivation was a mediating factor in this relationship (Gardner, 1985). Improved motivation has been associated with improved language learning results, such as improved speaking ability. Motivated students are more likely to look for communication chances and practice speaking. Additionally, attitudes toward language learning impact motivation, which in turn affects language learning success, particularly speaking performance, according to Gardner and Lambert (1972). Linguistic experts discuss whether language matters in the study of performance and whether performance should not be limited to competence. Chomsky (1965) defined performance as the practical use of language in everyday contexts, while Newby (2011) defined competence as the linguistic knowledge of the learner.

2. STATEMENTS OF THE PROBLEM

Speaking skill plays a vital role in different aspects of personal and academic development and it is a tool for communication. In his explanation of the importance of speaking in educational settings, Brown (2003) believes that one of the key language skills that aids in students' acquisition of language competency is speaking. Nunan (2003) describes communication as an interactive process of meaning development that encompasses information production, reception, and processing. He states that speaking is a necessary component of communication. It is critical for educators and policymakers to comprehend the relationship between speaking ability and these psychological factors motivation, and attitude if they hope to improve educational outcomes and promote learners' holistic development.

According to Gardner (1985), a crucial factor in considering a student's readiness for communication is motivation. As to Wakgari (2022), more motivated learners tend to speak English more effectively than those who are less motivated. Students with a positive attitude are eager to master the English language. On the other hand, students with a negative attitude lack eagerness for language learning. According to Promoduru (1992), an effective learner approaches the target language with positivity.

According to Azizifar (2014), successful students are those who have a positive attitude to learning a language. This indicates that students with a negative English-speaking attitude are likely to have low speaking proficiency.

From the researcher's experience of teaching students in high schools and universities students' speaking performance is low and a very serious concern as speaking is important for daily communication and even to get jobs. Some teachers and instructors have heard that though speaking is given as a course in universities and colleges and as a skill in English textbooks of high schools, it could not achieve its objective. Many students feel nervous or lack confidence when speaking, which can affect their fluency and coherence. From his experience, the researcher also witnessed that many students face problems in speaking and feel nervous, lack confidence, are unmotivated, stay reluctant, and keep silent during oral communication in classes. They frequently speak incoherently, pausing, repeating words, and making mistakes. At best, their speech reaches the word limit and takes the shape of brief, and inaccurate, and even they do not pronounce words correctly. Regarding this, it is thought that low students'

self-esteem, motivation, and attitude are the main factors for poor performance of students' speaking performance. Although numerous studies have been conducted globally on the relationship among motivation, attitude, and speaking performance, still there is a gap to be bridged in the Ethiopian context.

In this regard, two social psychologists globally, Gardner and Lambert (1972), carried out a series of investigations on L2 motivation and attitudes toward L2 proficiency. A study titled "The Correlation between Students' Self-esteem and Students' Speaking Ability in Grade 11" was conducted by Aisyah (2020). Rizqi Nur also (2022) conducted a study on the relationship between students' self-esteem and their speaking ability. Additionally, Kirli (2019) conducted a correlational study on students' motivation and speaking performance in Indonesia. Moreover, Lisanti Okta (2012) researched the correlation between students' attitudes toward learning English and their speaking ability in the case of grade 11.

Concerning local studies, Tamene (2000) states that there is a debate among teachers and researchers that secondary school English language proficiency is less than adequate to carry out numerous academic activities. Additionally, other local studies have indicated that students face problems even after they complete secondary school in using speaking skills for real communication. Some of these local studies are: Amanuel (2015) who researched the problems that affect students' English speaking skills and Mitiku (2021) conducted a study on the relationship between EFL Students' Speaking Strategies Use and their Speaking Proficiency. Tamene (2000) asserts that in oral communication students are forced to use their first language as an alternative. Taye (2008) and Jenenew (2006) conducted studies on how oral skills are taught.

Taye made a comparative study of televised and non-televised speaking skills teaching techniques. Jenenew conducted a survey study on teachers' and students' roles in the implementation of EFL-speaking classrooms. Furthermore, Taye (2015) conducted his research on the Effects of Cooperative Learning on EFL Students' Speaking Skills at the Tertiary Level. However, even if the studies mentioned above were conducted on speaking skills they are not correlational studies which are the relationship among motivation, attitude, and speaking performance.

It is expected that motivation and attitude have a relationship with students' speaking performance. Speaking is one of the four macro skills that has a significant role in communication as exemplified above. To make speaking performance successful students should have good motivation and attitude. Many EFL students face problems in learning English speaking which is related to psychological aspects of the students. In this study motivation and attitude were considered as the affective variables that contribute to speaking performance.

So far, in the Ethiopian context, no study has been conducted into the relationships among EFL students' motivation, attitude and speaking performance as far as the researcher's knowledge is concerned except that they were conducted on speaking skills by the above-mentioned researchers. Accordingly, this study is different from the above local studies due to the following reasons. First, this study differs from the studies mentioned above in bridging the gap that has not been filled yet. Second, the relationship among EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students' motivation, attitude, and speaking performance has been a topic of considerable interest and debate in the field of language learning and teaching.

Thirdly, the research setting and the context where the study was conducted was also different. Even though numerous studies suggest significant correlations between these variables, others present disagreeing findings or inconclusive results. For instance, Ananda (2017) investigated a study on the relationship between speaking abilities and students' self-

esteem. She conducted a study by administering questionnaires of self-esteem and speaking tests.

Lisanti (2021) conducted a study on the relationship between students' attitude and speaking ability in 11th grade of Senior High School 1 Ukui. The study found no significant correlation between students' attitude towards learning English and their speaking ability, contradicting the current study.

Therefore, as far as the researcher's knowledge involved the current study is the first to examine the relationship among the aforementioned variables and speaking performance in the Ethiopian high school setting and it is to disprove previous studies that claimed there was no relationship among students' motivation, attitude and speaking performance.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were addressed in this study.

- 3.1 What is the correlation between students' motivation and speaking performance?
- 3.2 What is the correlation between students' attitude and speaking performance?
- 3.3 Can EFL students' motivation and attitude predict speaking performance?

4. HYPOTHESIS

Based on the research questions above the following hypotheses were formulated to predict the relationship.

H0: There is no statistically significant relationship among EFL learners' motivation, attitude and speaking performance.

H1: There is a statistically significant relationship among EFL students' motivation, attitude and speaking performance.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research Design

This study employed the correlational research design to determine the relationship among the students' motivation, attitude, and speaking performance. Attitude and motivation are the predictor variable and speaking performance is the criterion variable.

5.2 Setting

The study was conducted in high schools of Addis Ketema sub-city in Addis Ababa city, Ethiopia. The city was chosen as it can represent and possibly reflect the status of the nation. Secondly, the researcher hoped that reliable information could be obtained from this city and that the distribution of the schools would make the study accessible.

5.3 Participants of the Study and Sampling Technique

The total population in this study was 671 students and consisted of 9 classes of Addis Ketema sub-city High Schools of Addis Ababa city which were enrolled in grade 11 in 2024. Accordingly, 87 students were selected as the sample of this study. A cluster sampling technique was used to choose the sample school. Frankel and Wallen (2009) state that cluster sampling differs from purposive sampling in that researchers only choose clusters, and it works more effectively if there are many clusters rather than a small number of individuals. Regarding students using a list of grade eleven students as a sampling frame, a systematic sampling approach was used to select participants from that school. Every *n*th person on the population list is chosen for the sample in a systematic sampling process (Frankel and Wallen, 2009).

5.4 Instruments and data collection

Two techniques were used to collect the data, these are questionnaires of self-esteem which were developed by Rosenberg (1979), motivation and attitude questionnaires which were developed by Gardner (1985) based on Motivation and Attitude Test Battery (AMTB), and attitude questionnaires were used which was developed by Gardner (1985) was used by using Likert scale and speaking test which was developed from grade 11 students' textbook was used. Self-esteem questionnaires are classified into two categories, which are 5 positive and 5 negative (Rosenberg, 1979).

The motivation questionnaire which comprises 20 questions and the attitude questionnaire which includes 30 questions were used in this study. Each item of the questionnaire has a five-point Likert scale, strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). Attitude and motivation questionnaires were employed since they are more valid to get more reliable data for these variables than other data-gathering tools. The researcher used Cronbach Alpha and SPSS version 24 to investigate the reliability of the questionnaires.

Speaking tests which were adapted from grade 11 students' English textbook was used to measure students' speaking performance. Those speaking tests were developed from students' textbook from each unit. Students' speaking performance was measured on four elements grammar and vocabulary (25%), pronunciation (25%), discourse management (25%), and interactive communication (25%). Regarding reliability and validity, the speaking test was checked.

In research, reliability is the ability to score consistently across different research projects (Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hayun, 2012, P. 154). Dependability, consistency, and reproducibility across time, instruments, and responder groups comprise reliability (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2007, P.146). For the study to persuade others, it must be reliable.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the study the following ideas were taken into consideration. The speaking tests were administered in the quiet classroom at Addis Ketema High School. The students were kept in another room waiting for their turns and the researcher with other teachers was organizing the tests. To keep the test safe students who took the test were not allowed to go back to the waiting room but rather leave the exam hall immediately and they were tested individually on their speaking performance. In this regard, their performance in speaking was recorded by the examiners, and each student was given marks on four components (grammar and vocabulary, pronunciation, discourse management, and interactive communication) based on the scoring rubric developed by Brown (2004). Before administration, this test was seen and checked by the supervisors of the study for reliability. Moreover, the students were also tested by the same examiners, and the students' name was kept confidential and coded when their score was given.

5.5 Data analysis

The quantitative data was used to determine whether there is any positive correlation between students' motivation, and students' speaking performance or not. It was entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 for data analysis. Multiple regression was employed as the number of predictor variables is 2 and the criterion variable is 1. The researcher analyzed and interpreted the data quantitatively. Creswell (2012) states that correlational design allows predicting scores and describing the relationship between variables. Accordingly, in this study, the researcher employed descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the quantitative data to describe the relationship between those variables.

6. NORMAL DISTRIBUTION OF DATA AND ALT TEXT

Figure 1 Caption: Scatter Plot Figure 1 Alt Text:

This scatter plot in Figure 1 indicates that the distribution of the data is normal as the data are distributed above and below the fit line. Hence, the figure depicts data that are normally distributed to conduct correlation and regression.

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Figure 2 Caption: Histogram of motivation, attitude, and speaking performance.

Figure 2 Alt Text:
 The histogram in Figure 2 also depicted the normal distributions of the variables and it implies that data are normally distributed.

Figure 3 Caption: P-P plot Figure 3 Alt Text:

The P-P Plot in Figure 3 depicted also normal distribution of the data. However, there are values roughly shouldered. Hence, the above figure reveals the normality of data which is near the fit line.

7. RESULTS

7.1 ANALYSIS OF ATTITUDE

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics means students' attitude						
	N	Minimum		Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
	87	1.73		4.37	2.9	0.53
	Score for items (range)	Participants	Percent	Classification of self-esteem judgment Range of score ≥ 3.0 positive self-esteem, ≤ 3.0 negative self-esteem		
1	1.73-2.80	39	44.83%	Negative		
2	2.83—3.00	15	17.24%	Negative		
3	3.03-3.27	14	16.09%	Positive		
4	3.30-3.73	13	14.95%	Positive		
5	3.8-4.37	6	6.89%	Positive		
Total		87	100			

Table 1 shows motivation of the students was obtained, and it was found that the mean is 2.9 and the standard deviation is 0.53. The results also revealed that 62.07% of students were

negative in speaking performance. In contrast, 37.93% of students were positive in attitude of speaking performance.

7.2 Analysis of Motivation

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics means students' motivation						
	N	Minimum		Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
	87	1		5	3.1	.741
	Score for items (range)	Participants	Percent	Classification of self-esteem judgment Range of score > 3.0 positive self-esteem, <3.0 negative self-esteem		
1	1.00-2.00	17	19.55%	Negative		
2	2.01-3.00	39	44.82%	Negative		
3	3.04-3.74	9	10.34%	Positive		
4	3.75-5	22	25.29%	Positive		
Total		87	100			

Table 2 shows the motivation of the students was obtained, and it was found that the mean is 3.1, and the standard deviation is 0.741. The results also revealed that 64.37% of students were negative in motivation of speaking performance. In contrast, 35.63% of students were positive in motivation of speaking performance.

7.3 Analysis of Speaking Performance Test range of score

The students' speaking performance score scale was based on Brown (2004).

Table 3. The system of students' scoring scale				
	Score range	Category	Score	Percent
1	96-100	Excellent	-	-
2	81-95	Very good	-	-
3	61-80	Good	29	33.34%
4	41-60	Fair	57	65.52%
5	21-40	Poor	1	1.14%
6	0-20	Very poor	-	-
Total			87	100%

As can be seen from Table 3 above 33.34 % of grade 11 students were in the good category, 65.52% of students in the fair category, and 1.14% of students in the poor category.

Table 4. Maximum, minimum, mean, and Std. deviation					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Speaking Performance test	87	37	80	58	8.877
Valid (listwise)	87				

Based on Table 4 above the mean of the speaking performance test was 58, and the standard deviation was 8.877.

7.4 Descriptive analysis of speaking performance

Descriptive data in Table 6 below depicts the variables under consideration in the study. Four components of the speaking performance (100%) and their maximum and minimum mean of (25%) results were shown in the table. The results illustrate the means (average of variables' scores), the standard deviation (the difference between variables' scores and the mean), and the range of each variable describing the minimum and maximum values.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Speaking Performance Test

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Speaking Performance Test					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Grammar and vocabulary	87	10	20	14.6	2.313
Pronunciation	87	8	21	14.4	2.662
Discourse management	87	9	21	14.8	2.463
Interactive communication	87	8	20	14.2	2.420
Valid N (listwise)	87				

Table 6, indicates that the lowest score (minimum) obtained in grammar and vocabulary is 10 points the Maximum is 20 and the mean score of 14.6 is also the average of all scores in grammar and vocabulary gained by each of the 87 students. The table also indicates that the lowest score obtained by pronunciation is 8 the maximum is 21 and the mean score of 14.4 is the average of all students' scores obtained by each of the students.

Additionally, descriptive data in Table 6 above depicts the variables under consideration in the study. Four components of the speaking performance (100%) and their maximum and minimum mean of (25%) results were shown in the table. The results illustrate the means (average of variables' scores), the standard deviation (the difference between variables' scores and the mean), and the range of each variable describing the minimum and maximum values. Additionally, the table also reveals that the lowest score got by discourse management was 9 points the maximum was 21 and the mean score 14.8 was the average of all students' scores gained by each of the students. The last was Interactive communication and the table shows that the minimum score obtained was 8 points and the maximum was 20. The mean score of 14.2 was the average of all students' scores obtained by each student. In this regard, the mean scores have fallen in –between 14.8 and 14.2 which are very near to each other. From the above table, it can be concluded that the average mean of the four components is 14.5% out of 25%.

8. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATION AMONG, ATTITUDE, MOTIVATION AND SPEAKING PERFORMANCE

8.1 Correlation between Speaking Performance and Attitude Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Speaking test	14.50	2.14	87
Attitude	2.90	.540	87

Table 11: Descriptive statistics of Addis Ketema high school students' speaking performance and their Motivation (N=87)

It is shown that in Table 11, the total population of the students is 87, the mean score of the speaking test is 14.5 and the mean score of attitude is 2.90. Moreover, the standard deviation of the speaking test is 2.14 and the standard deviation of attitude is .540.

Correlations			
		Speaking test	Attitude
Speaking test	Pearson Correlation	1	.828**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	87	87
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.828**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	87	87

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12: The relationship between students’ speaking performance and attitude (N=87)

It is indicated that in Table 12, there was a statistically significant positive relationship between students’ speaking performance and their attitude which is $r = .828$ and the p -value is $=0.000$ which is less than 0.05 (<0.05). Hence, the correlation between attitude and speaking performance is effective with a coefficient correlation of $.828$ at a significance level of 0.01 . The correlation coefficient value of 0.828 is shown in the output results above. It can be inferred from the above table that there is a relationship between speaking performance and students' attitudes.

The output results also show that the coefficient value is positive (0.828), signifying that there is a positive correlation between speaking performance and the attitude of the students.

According to the results shown above, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted and it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between students' attitude and their speaking performance as the Pearson correlation is 0.828 . Accordingly, based on the findings shown above the relationship among motivation, attitude, and speaking performance was positive which 0.449 , and 0.828 respectively. Therefore, there is a significant relationship among attitude, motivation, and speaking performance, all null hypotheses were rejected, and the alternative hypothesis were accepted. Moreover, the researcher conducted a regression analysis to know the influences between independent variables and dependent variable.

8.2. Correlation between speaking performance and motivation

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Speaking test	14.50	2.135	87
Motivation	3.10	.741	87

Table 9: Descriptive statistics of Addis Ketema high school students’ speaking performance and their Motivation (N=87)

As depicted in Table 9 above, the total population of the participants is 87, the mean score of the speaking test is 14.5 and the mean score of motivation is 3.10. Additionally, it indicates that the standard deviation of speaking test and motivation is 2.135 and .741 respectively.

Table 10: The relationship between students' speaking performance and Motivation (N=87)

Correlations			
		Speaking test	Motivation
Speaking test	Pearson Correlation	1	.449**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	87	87
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.449**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	87	87

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It is indicated that in Table 10, there was a statistically significant positive relationship between students' speaking performance and their motivation which is .449, and the p-value is =0.000 which is less than 0.05 (<0.05). Hence, the correlation between motivation and speaking performance is effective with a coefficient correlation of .449 at a significance level of 0.01. Based on the findings mentioned above, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between students' motivation and their speaking performance since the Pearson correlation is 0.449 and the significance value is =0.000 which is less than 0.05.

9. REGRESSION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Attitude, Motivation ^b	.	Enter
a. Dependent Variable: Speaking test			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Table 13 indicates that the variables entered are independent variables attitude and motivation and the dependent variable which is speaking performance.

Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.847 ^a	.718	.711	1.147
a. Predictors: (Constant), Attitude, Motivation				

Table 14: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

R in a regression analysis is the correlation coefficient and it is defined as the correlation between an independent and a dependent variable which is .847. R square in Table 14 shows the total variance or collective effect of all independent variables on the dependent variable. It ranges from 0 to 1 and is obtained by squaring the R-value.

In this context, R is .847, and $(.847)^2 = .718$. Hence, in this model .718 implies that 71.8 % of the speaking performance of the students can be explained by attitude and motivation.

In other words, the coefficient of determination R square indicates 71.8 % of the change in speaking performance was explained by the independent variables attitude and motivation. However, the other 28.2% of the speaking performance of the students was not explained in this model which was residual. The SPSS adjusted R square for 71.1% of the variation was explained by the regression line.

Table 15: The results of ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	281.571	2	140.786	106.971	.000 ^b
	Residual	110.554	84	1.316		
	Total	392.125	86			
a. Dependent Variable: Speaking test						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Attitude, Motivation						

As shown above, in Table 15, the results of ANOVA reveal that the model reached statistical significance $F = 106.971$, and $p = 0.000 < 0.001$.

This means that there is a significant relationship between independent variables (attitude and motivation) and the dependent variable speaking performance. The results of the ANOVA model also align with Table 14, above that in this model if we divide the sum of squares of the regression 281.571 by a total 392.125 the result is .718 which reveals the speaking performance of the students (71.8%) was explained by those variables attitude and motivation. This implies that (28.2%) was not explained in this model.

10. DISCUSSION

The main objective of this research is to study the relationship among EFL students' motivation, attitude, and speaking performance of students of English as a foreign language in Ethiopia. The specific objectives of this research were: To examine the relationship between students' motivation and speaking performance, to identify the relationship between students' attitude and speaking performance, and identify whether the students' motivation and attitude can predict speaking performance.

The correlation between motivation and speaking performance is positive with a correlation coefficient of 0.449 at a significant level of 0.01. The correlation between attitude and speaking performance is positive, with a 0.828 correlation coefficient at a significant level of 0.01. The degree of correlation between motivations with speaking was moderate while the degree of correlation between attitude and speaking performance was high. Hence, the null hypothesis that motivation, and attitude of Ethiopian EFL students do not have a significant relationship with the speaking performance in this study was rejected. From these two independent variables attitude is the stronger predictor of speaking performance with a correlation coefficient of 0.828 and a significance level of 0.01.

Research question 1, examined the correlation between students' motivation and speaking performance. According to Krashen (1981), students who have high levels of motivation are more likely to succeed in learning foreign languages. The correlation between students' attitudes and speaking performance was 0.449 which was significant at 0.01 (2-tailed) and all null hypothesis was rejected.

The result of the study revealed that 64.35% of the Ethiopian EFL students' motivation level was low in Table 2. This implies that it is expected from teachers to advance students' motivation in speaking. Language teachers may be the only model of the target language that

students encounter, which is consistent with the assertion made by motivational research that they are the most significant factor influencing students' speaking motivational levels in many EFL situations (Dörnyei, 2001; Dörnyei & Csizér, 1998; Noels, 2001; Vibulphol, 2016; Woodrow, 2017).

To answer research question number 2, the correlation between students' attitudes and speaking performance the data collected from the Attitude Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) by Gardner (1985) which comprises 30 Likert-scale items and speaking performance tests were used. The correlation between students' attitudes and speaking performance was 0.828 which was significant at 0.01 (2-tailed) and all null hypothesis was rejected.

To answer question number 3, Can EFL students' motivation and attitude predict speaking performance? Regression analysis was done to know whether motivation, and attitude can predict the speaking performance of the students. Based on the results of the study obtained from questionnaires and speaking test independent variables (motivation and attitude) revealed change explained 71.8% of speaking performance and the other 28.2% was not explained in the model of this study.

11. CONCLUSION

The following conclusion can be drawn from this study. The study conducted on the correlation between attitude, motivation and speaking performance provided valuable understandings into the relationship among these variables. The findings of this study suggest some useful conclusions:

According to the conclusion of this study there is positive correlation between attitude and speaking performance.

The first is relationship between attitudes and speaking performance which indicates that there was significant relationship between them and according to the research the Pearson correlation is 0.828 and the significance value is 0.000. This indicates that attitude has a pivotal role in predicting speaking performance and it is the strongest predictor of speaking performance. The second is relationship between motivation and speaking performance. The study highlights the significant contribution of motivation in speaking performance and there was significant relationship between them as the Pearson correlation is 0.449 and significant value is ($P < 0.05$). By and large, this study reveals the potential relationship among attitude motivation and speaking performance. By explaining this relationships, this study can contribute to our understanding of the psychological dynamics underlying effective speaking which provides valuable understanding for both theory and practice. Despite this relationship there was no study which was conducted on the correlation between these predictive variables (attitude and motivation) and speaking performance.

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Ethics statement

The Research Ethics Review Committee of Hawassa University, College of Social sciences, approved this study and Humanities, with ethics approval reference number CSSH/301/2024.

Additionally, written informed Consent was obtained from all participants for the study. All the participants of the study were above 18 years and parental consent was not required.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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